

THE IMPORTANCE OF GIVING FEEDBACK TO STUDENTS

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Feedback is considered to be an important part of classroom interaction. It is important for students to know how well they are doing as they learn. This is because the knowledge that they are doing well gives students a sense of achievement which motivates them to learn more. Similarly, it is also important to let students know when they have made a mistake so that they will learn from it and take corrective measures. Hence, it is absolutely essential for teachers to monitor students' learning and give them feedback. Even it is necessary to receive feedback for the teachers from their peers so that to improve the quality of their teaching process.

Quality teaching and student performance are key matters of concern to educators and broader stakeholders everywhere. We know from a vast range of studies that the teacher is the major in-school influence on student achievement. However improving teacher effectiveness and lifting student achievement can seem daunting. How can we up-scale the incidence of highly effective teachers and schools? Many international research studies of student achievement have been subject to meta-analyses with revealing findings. In almost every list of effect sizes for 'treatments' influencing student achievement, feedback is at or near the top of those treatments which have greatest effect on student learning. What then is feedback? In the context of teaching and learning, feedback can be defined as any form of response by a teacher to a student's performance, attitude or behavior, at least where attitude or behavior impinges upon performance. It is important to realize that feedback is not only an outcome of student performance but an essential part of the learning process. It is also important not to confuse feedback on performance with 'positive reinforcement', self-esteem 'boosting' praise, or punishment. Feedback can be written or spoken and may even be gestural, indicating approval, encouragement or criticism. There is also scope for peer feedback (student-student feedback) and for students to provide feedback to a teacher on that teacher's performance (student-teacher feedback). Teachers can also receive feedback on their performance from peers (teacher-teacher feedback) or

supervisors (supervisor-teacher feedback). More rarely, supervisors receive feed-back from their staff (staff-supervisor feedback).

When we consider learning or mastery in fields as diverse as sports, the arts, languages, the sciences or recreational activities, it is easy to see how important feedback is to learning and accomplishment. An expert teacher, mentor or coach can readily explain, demonstrate and detect flaws in performance. He or she can also identify talent and potential and build on these. In contrast, trial and error learning or poor teaching are less effective and take longer. If performance flaws are not detected and corrected, these can become ingrained and will be much harder to eradicate later. Learners who don't receive instruction, encouragement and correction can become disillusioned and quit due to lack of progress. Feedback is equally vital in schooling and performs a variety of functions including recognizing, correcting, and encouraging, challenging and improving student performance. Feedback also keeps students 'on track' and is an aid to classroom management.

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An important dimension of feedback is its immediacy. The longer the time gap between the completion of the work and its feedback, the less effective the feedback becomes. Ideally, feedback should be provided within minutes after the completion of a task (e.g. immediately after a student asks or answers a question). Teachers can use non-verbal gestures to indicate their intention; they can nod their heads, use facial expressions or hand gestures to prompt the student to continue, or adopt a physical stance that signals their readiness to move on. Teachers should vary their reactions to students' answers; they can restate what the student has said to reinforce the point, ask for clarification, invite the student to elaborate, acknowledge the student's contribution but ask for another view, or nod their heads but remain silent.

Teachers should give credit to students for correct answers, but be aware that most students will stop thinking about a question once the instructor has indicated that someone's response is correct. However, teachers should correct

wrong answers tactfully, and encourage the student to rephrase or revise the answer. If a student needs assistance in answering a question, teachers should look to other students to provide help rather than providing it themselves.

Feedback should also be given to students as frequently as possible. Ideally, a student should receive feedback for each and every assigned task in the process of acquiring proficiency with new material. Teachers should try to give feedback in a positive manner as positive feedback not only provides more information than negative ones but it also helps to strengthen a student's motivation and self-esteem. A positive approach should also be adopted when providing students with feedback on their mistakes.

One of the most valuable aspects of effective feedback is its ability to foster learner autonomy. Students tend to become self regulated learners when they are provided with detailed feedback on performance as well as guidance for future improvement. Evidence of this self-regulatory process can be seen in an increasing ability to align aspects of thinking, motivation and behaviour with assessment criteria, standards and learning outcomes as well as learning goals established by the learners themselves.

Another factor that may influence the effectiveness of feedback is whether it is provided continuously or differentially. When continuous feedback is employed, students receive feedback each time they perform a given task, whereas differential feedback is only provided when a student performs better on the task. One advantage that differential feedback offers over continuous feedback is that it emphasizes improvement rather than a student's absolute level of achievement. Hence, all students have a near equal chance of obtaining recognition. When feedback is geared to the absolute level of performance, recognition is only given to the best students. Therefore, it is generally good to give students feedback when they show improvement.

The research evidence is clear: great teachers give great feedback, and every teacher is capable of giving more effective feedback. As an aside, it also stands to reason that if a student doesn't know where he or she stands and how he or she can improve, then parents will have even less of an idea and will be poorly equipped to assist and provide support to both student and teacher.

Making conclusion we can say that teacher feedback can assist learners to notice a target structure, to compare it with their existing knowledge and to integrate it into that knowledge. Peer feedback, on the other hand, can also help learners to notice the target structure while reconfirming its use and providing additional input via the learners' input. It became clear that Feedback is

considered to be an essential part of education and training programmes. It helps learners to maximise their potential at different stages of training, raise their awareness of strengths and areas for improvement, and identify actions to be taken to improve performance.

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